

E-Learning Adoption in Higher Education During Covid-19, A Comparative Analysis between Graduate and Undergraduate Students

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Abstract: A vibe on research regarding the intention of using online learning during the COVID-19 crisis has got a spike. The drive of this study was to investigate the comparative analysis on the factors that influence the attitudes and willingness to use online learning platforms between graduate and undergraduate students with the extended application of the TAM model. As the research design, a deductive and quantitative research approach has been applied and tested the hypotheses on the data collected on 338 students from various public and private universities in Bangladesh. To conduct the data analysis, the partial least squares-structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) was used and SmartPLS version 3.2.7 software was administrated. The relationship between SN and intention to use, PEOU, or PU along with CSE with PU and PU with students' intention to adopt e-learning has a similar effect considering graduate and undergraduate students. Quite the reverse, the relationship between Computer Self-Efficacy (CSE) with PEOU and students' intention to use e-learning technology showed significantly different result considering graduate and undergraduate students.

Keywords: Online learning; TAM Model; Comparison, higher education

JEL Codes: A22, A23

Introduction

COVID-19 crisis, the most recent terrible situation was shaken the whole world dreadfully including Bangladesh. All sorts of people in every field, especially students all over the world are affected negatively not only from academic perspectives but also by mental health issues that adversely impact their learning process as well as academic performance (Mailizar et al., 2020). The shutdown of educational institutions all over the world to maintain social distancing forced the conversion of conventional education to virtual learning but truly that could not happen successfully overnight and is linked to various obstacles and challenges (Crawford et al., 2020). As the disappearance of this pandemic is fully unknown, educational institutions all over the world started using the available

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technical resources to generate online learning for students of all academic fields as a continuation of academic activities (Kaur, 2020). In Bangladesh, as well, the conveyance of classes through the internet using the online platform has been a recent addition brought out by most of the educational institutions and becoming an integral part now. Education has become more convenient and accessible due to online channels (Nambiar, 2020). The study also reported the opportunity to explore and use innovative teaching methods through online channels. Nonetheless, some limitations were also observed and experienced regarding technology use which leads to a negative influence on attendance and participation in online sessions and created the medium challenging. However, fruitful pedagogical use of technology highly depends on the users' attitudes and acceptance of technology. Introduced by Davis in 1989, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) has been the most extensively espoused theoretical framework to investigate technology acceptance in all sorts of sectors.

Brezavšček et al. (2014) recommended that the TAM model is most suitable for students with great value for educators that enable them to improve the learning process. Besides, Zhao et al. (2018) propose a research model with an extended TAM model and showed all the TAM factors have a significant influence on user acceptance. Most importantly the study's respondents were 90 percent undergraduate. Furthermore, among UK undergraduate students the TAM factors relationship among (SE-PEOU, SN-PEOU, PEOU-PU, PU-behavioural intention, and PEOU- behavioral intention) was only found significant (Abdullah et al., 2016). Not only that the studies conducted both from teaching staff and students' perspectives on e-learning in higher education during COVID-19 and both groups were agreed that e-learning will not be a fruitful students assessment process and for practical lessons. Rather they have a negative expectation and need more training and workshop on e-learning (Abdullah & Abdullah, 2021). On the contrary, 1,904 undergraduate students at Chilean University reported positive experience in online teaching and learning although their expectations were also low (Lobos et al., 2022). In Bangladesh, public university students showed more positive perceptions of those who have personal laptops or computers than mobile users (Sarkar et al., 2021). The mass adoption of technology is not easy in a developing country like Bangladesh. The use of technology in the education sector has increased dramatically during the pandemic. Many students failed to equip enough infrastructure to attend e-learning due to financial crisis which created an adverse effect on their academic performance in both the short term and long run (Sharmin et al., 2020).

Different studies showed the practice and effectiveness of e-learning using the TAM model (Brezavšček et al., 2014; Cakır & Solak, 2015; Farahat, 2012; Lazim et al., 2021; Mailizar et al., 2020; Masrom, 2007; Noh et al., 2021; Salloum et al., 2019; Zhao et al., 2018) in an overall context as well as between different groups for example between gender, among ages, between teaching staff and students, etc. Therefore, some researchers explained the effectiveness of e-learning metamorphosing among age groups, especially between children and younger (Li & Lalani, 2020). Nevertheless, this study tries to show the differences in the perception of the adoption of e-learning between the level of education (graduate, and undergraduate) using the TAM model adapted from Yuen and Ma (2008) which was originally proposed by Davis et al. (1989).

Literature Review

E-Learning Technology

Kelly (2001) denotes online learning as asynchronous or self-paced learning. Broadly speaking, e-learning states the usage of internet technologies to bring a broad range of solutions that boost knowledge and performance (Rosenberg, 2001). Presently, e-learning has grandiose uses in all sectors from businesses to educational institutions (Tamm, 2020). It can build a strong relationship between the learners and instructors in a cost-efficient manner. E-learning is founded on three central standards: (1) it is networked for instant updating, storage/retrieval, distribution, and sharing of instruction or information; (2) it is transported to the end-user through the computer using standard internet technology; and (3) its emphases on the widest view of learning solutions that surpass the conventional patterns of training (Rosenberg, 2001, p. 28). E-learning technology explores the potential of engagement in new ways and offers innovative pedagogies. (Yuen & Ma, 2008). But the prime concern is about the reliability of the learning services and the availability of resources needed in e-learning systems (Salloum et al., 2019; Schroeder et al., 2010). Nambiar (2020) came up with some areas which are important for teacher and student satisfaction with online classes, these areas are quality and timely interaction between student and professor, technical support availability, structured online class modules, and modifications to accommodate conduction of practical classes.

E-Learning Technology in Higher Education During COVID-19

Before COVID-19, the adaptation of e-learning in education was already a growing concern. Notwithstanding COVID, educational institutions around the world are closing down in the first half of 2020. Hence, e-learning activities have grown more drastically than before to continue the educational activities through distance learning. In response to rising demand, many online platforms made free access for their services. Around the world, e-learning is considered the best solution for present teaching and learning need in higher education (Almulla, 2021). Despite its usefulness, the short notice to switch to e-learning created stress and anxiety among students (Müller, 2021). However, many students are lagging and have made a huge difference between technology-privileged students and non-privileged students due to a lack of resources and new applications on digital platforms (Li & Lalani, 2020).

In Bangladesh from October 2021 universities began to reopen their campuses. Nevertheless, most universities conducted their activities both online and physically. Even, both public and private universities agree that they want to use a hybrid or blended approach in the future, as teachers and students have already adapted to online teaching. They predict that technology will play a massive role in education (Arannya, 2021). Another study was conducted by Othman Abdullah and Mahmood Abdullah (2021) among public universities in Bangladesh and found students didn't recognize the effectiveness of e-learning because of a lack of access to the internet, devices, and resources for e-learning. On the other hand, the teaching staff has enough resources and access to e-learning. Notwithstanding, both groups were a consensus that it is less fruitful than the practical lesson.

Understanding TAM Model

In order to investigate technology acceptance, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) has been extensively recognized across the world to construct a theoretical framework. The model was introduced by Davis back in 1989 as an adaptation of the “Theory of Reasoned Action” (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1980), more specifically modified for demonstrating user acceptance of information systems. According to this model, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use are theorized to be the prime elements of user technology acceptance (Davis, 1989). TAM model is used to develop the core framework of this study but the extension of this model has been framed for portraying the more specific phenomenon of the exploration of online-learning technology acceptance amongst students. Therefore, ‘computer self-efficacy’ of users and ‘subjective norm’ of the users’ have been accommodated into the conceptual framework after reviewing relevant literature extensively (Hall & Higgins, 2005; Ma et al., 2005; Teo et al., 2008; Venkatesh et al., 2003).

Human beings are generally coherent with rationality and use the available information systematically, this is the assumption of the Theory of Reasoned Action. Therefore, in the decision to engage or not to engage in a given behavior, the implications of their immediate actions are considered by the individuals. According to this theory, an individual would generally act in accord with his or her intention which has two basic determinants, one person in nature and the other reflecting social influence. The personal factor is the attitude toward behavior based on the judgment referred to as the positive or negative evaluation of performing the behavior. Social pressures to perform or not to perform the behavior determines the second determinant. Subjective norm refers to the intention to perform a behavior when an individual evaluates it positively and worth as important (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1980).

Social cognitive theory (Compeau & Higgin, 1995; Compeau et al., 1999) placed forward the concept of self-efficacy which refers to one’s beliefs about the ability to perform a specific behavior with the expectation of positive outcomes. The theory propositions that the degree to use the technology depends on the capability to use technology successfully. Likewise, social cognitive theory explicitly recognizes the existence of a continuous reciprocal interaction between the environment in which an individual functions his or her reasoning perceptions (self-efficacy and outcome expectations) and behavior (Bandura, 1986). In this way, whether the interaction would be successful with technology depends on the influences on self-efficacy.

Conducive to ascertain and demonstrate the factors affecting the acceptance of e-learning have several variants in technology adoption theories, for instance, Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), Task Technology Fit (TTF), Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), and Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). It can be said that amongst these theories, TAM is the cornerstone of the literature on e-learning acceptance (Lai, 2017; Šumak et al., 2011; p.2068). Although the original TAM model was introduced by Davis in 1989, it was also revised by Davis et al. (1989) in the same year. The original TAM model is presented in the below figure.

Figure 1: Original TAM model by Davis, 1989

In this model perceived usefulness, and perceived ease of use are predictors of the attitude of the user, posterior behavioral intentions, and actual usage (Davis, 1989).

Hypothesis Development

In light of that, the purpose of this study was to investigate the factors that influence the attitudes and willingness to use online learning platforms among the graduate and undergrad students during the COVID-19 crisis with the use of the TAM model. This study used a framework of the TAM model to analyze the student's level of acceptance of e-learning, which was previously developed by Yuen and Ma (2008). TAM model has been modified several times since the initial version of the TAM model. Venkatesh and Davis (2000) provide a framework that links perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use to behavioral intention, eliminating attitudes toward it. In addition, the researcher found that perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use strongly determine the intention to use. Therefore, Perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use were the core constructs in the framework, and additional variables such as intention to use, subjective norm, and computer self-efficacy were added in order to paradigm a well-constructed model for better understanding of the students' acceptance of online learning which finally tested to analyze the hypothesis.

Figure 2: Research Framework (adapted by Yuen and Ma, 2008)

Student's Subjective Norm (SN)

A subjective norm (SN) denotes a type of belief that a person or group of people who is important to you will approve of and support a certain behavior. In other words, it motivates individuals to comply with people's views (Ham et al., 2015). A meta-analysis investigated by BAKI et al., (2018) about 203 studies of e-learning acceptance using the TAM model proposed a direct significant influence of subjective norm as an external variable on perceived usefulness which ranked 27 among 129 different external variables. Besides the studies showed the influence of SN on PEOU with the rank of 9. Where PEOU denotes the individuals' perception about the facilitating use of the technology (Davis et al., 1989). Another study conducted by Abdullah et al. (2016) with GETAMEL in the context of e-portfolios found a significant correlation between SN and PEOU as in previous studies. But unexpectedly recommend that some researchers found no strong evidence between SN and PU among undergraduate students in the UK.

H1a: SN has a significant positive effect on PU and the impact has a significant difference between graduate and undergraduate students' perception of e-learning technology.

H1b: SN has a significant positive effect on PEOU and the impact has a significant difference between graduate and undergraduate students' perception of e-learning technology.

According to planned behaviour theory, the intention of a certain behaviour is directly influenced by three factors one is intentions, attitude, and subjective norms (Neighbors et al., 2013). But the controversy in the previous studies is SN is weaker than the influence of attitude (Ham et al., 2015). On the other hand, another study by Hussein et al. (2018) mentioned SN as an important determinant of behavioural intentions, and the reason behind that they reflect the influence of the other. Therefore, the study among graduate students who have already worked for several years found a moderate correlation between SN and behavioural intention (Hussein, 2018).

H1c: SN has a significant positive effect on the intention to accept e-learning technology and the impact has a significant difference between the perceptions of graduate and undergraduate students.

Student's Computer Self-Efficacy

Students' computer self-efficacy (CSE) is the reasoning ability to use a computer. Individuals who have a higher CSE belief are supposed to see themselves as capable of using the computer (Compeau & Higgins 1995, p. 192). According to BAKI (2018) investigation, SE influence both PU and PEOU but PEOU is not affected by computer anxiety. Another study found a significant effect of SE on PU and PEOU. Unexpectedly, showed a negative relationship between SE and PU and predict the reason behind those students who are confident to use e-technology but do not find its actual usefulness (Abdullah et al., 2016). If a student has a positive perception of CSE, they can realize its benefit more than those who have not. Not only that CSE's direct effect on PEOU is higher than the direct effect of PU (Thongsri et al., 2020). Another study among 500 people in Indonesia also confirmed a significant influence of CSE on both PU and PEOU (M. Bus et

al., 2020). On the other hand, the absolute findings by Abdullah et al. (2016) among the higher education students of Saudi Arabia, which is only found the influence of CSE on PEOU. Besides the relationship between CSE and PU is not significant (Binyamin et al., 2019). Furthermore, Clayton et al. (2017) found low computer self-efficacy among undergraduate students. Now we assume the following hypotheses-

H2a: General CSE has a significant positive effect on PU and the impact has a significant difference between graduate and undergraduate students' perception of e-learning technology.

H2b: General CSE has a significant positive effect on PEOU and the impact has a significant difference between graduate and undergraduate students' perception of e-learning technology.

CSE has both effects on PU and PEOU but the effect among different disciplines is varying (Thongsri et al., 2019), but individuals with high CSE will perceive more useful to use than perceived with low CSE. On the contrary Clayton et al. (2017) mentioned low self-efficacy among undergraduate students. Therefore, Yuen and Ma (2008) didn't find the influence of CSE on intention to use e-learning technology among teachers' acceptance of e-learning. Although they mentioned CSE is another important determinant of intention to use e-learning technology. Therefore, a study among 670 learners found a significant effect of self-efficacy on the intention to use e-learning. The study also confirmed an important thing that is they found the factors were varied according to different degrees of learner's participation (Chang et al., 2015).

H2c: General CSE has a significant positive effect on the intention to accept e-learning technology and the impact has a significant difference between graduate and undergraduate students' perceptions.

Student's Perceived Ease of use

Perceived ease of use (PEOU) is a fundamental determinant of an individual's acceptance and intention to use, likewise having a significant influence on both of them (Yuen and Ma, 2008; Saadé et al., 2008). Farther, it facilitates an important predictor for most educational institutions. A study conducted among the students in Indonesia Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) during COVID-19, found the critical influence of PEOU on PU, and intentions to use e-learning technology (Sukendro et al., 2020). Abdullah et al. (2016) found both significant impacts of PEOU on PU and behavioral intention among undergraduate students. Moreover, individuals' differences affect PEOU positively in forwarding PEOU dominant positively on both PU and behavioral intention of the individual (Ji et al., 2019). Therefore, we assume the following hypothesis.

H3a: PEOU has a significant positive influence on PU and the impact has a significant difference between graduate and undergraduate students' perception of e-learning technology.

H3b: PEOU has a more significant positive effect on their intention to accept e-learning technology and the impact has a significant difference between graduate and undergraduate students' perceptions.

Student's Perceived Usefulness

According to Davis (1989), Perceived usefulness (PU) prescribed the individuals' belief in the usefulness of a certain technology. If learners avowed the ease of e-learning or they can perceive that e-learning is easy to use, they will be more encouraged to use e-learning technology (Thongsri et al., 2019). A previous study conducted by Saadé et al. (2008) among Canadian universities exerts no direct significant relationship between PU and behavioral intention to use. Though Abdullah et al. (2016) found significant influence among undergraduate students. Elsewhere, some researchers asserted that perceived usefulness directly influences intention to use (Ji et al., 2019). Overall, we predict that-

H4: PU has a significant positive effect on their intention to accept e-learning technology and the impact has a significant difference between graduate and undergraduate students' perceptions.

Methodology

Study Instrument

After an all-inclusive literature review, a pre-validated questionnaire was adapted from Yuen and Ma (2008) and finalized based on the characteristics of the respondents and informal discussions with two academicians (one from the management field and the other from the social science discipline), one research expert and five students (from diversified discipline) considering their feedback. All items were measured on a 5-point Likert scale from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree". Students were asked to respond to the questions in google form related to their perception regarding online classes during pandemic situations from November 2021 to December 2021. Both undergraduate and post-graduate students have been approached to explore the differences in perception.

Table1

Research instruments

Variables	No. of items	Source
Subjective Norm (SN)	3	Adapted from Yuen and Ma (2008), and originally from Fishbein and Ajzen (1975)
Computer Self-efficacy (SE)	6	Adapted from Yuen and Ma (2008), and originally from Compeau and Higgins (1999)
Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)	4	Adapted from Yuen and Ma (2008), and originally from Davis (1989)
Perceived Usefulness (PU)	5	Adapted from Yuen and Ma (2008), and originally from Davis (1989)
Intention to Use (ITU)	3	Adapted from Yuen and Ma (2008), and originally from Fishbein and Ajzen (1975)

The domain of the Study

At the very beginning, we identified key informants from business schools among different public universities for an online survey. Participants had to be current students in higher education (undergrad, graduate) from Bangladesh, set as inclusion criteria for the study. A

Google form was prepared and the link was sent to the key informants through WhatsApp and messenger. The study adopted snowball sampling as the key informants submitted their responses and circulated the link using their network. The link has been disabled after 30 days of circulating the Google forms. We had received 412 responses from the respondents among them 338 were selected for the final analysis. Among them, 134 respondents were graduate level and 204 respondents were from undergraduate level.

We used G*Power to compute the sample size based on statistical power (Faul et al. 2009). Based on the computation a sample size of 129 was required for model testing with a statistical power of 0.95 for each of the groups for comparison. As a result of our sample size exceeding 129, the power value for this investigation was also more than 0.95. Additionally, in social and behavioural science research, the minimum necessary power is often 0.8 (Rasoolimanesh et al., 2016). As a result, we can fairly infer that our sample sizes for each group were enough for the objectives of this study in both circumstances.

Data analysis

The respondents' answers were taken for further steps of calculation only if they had answered all the questions. After filling up the questionnaire in google form, the aggregated result was available in Google Sheet, which was downloaded as an Excel sheet. To conduct the data analysis, the partial least squares-structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) and Multi-Group Analysis (MGA) were used and Smart PLS V.3.2.7 software was administrated. The collected data were analyzed following a two-step assessment approach - structural model and measurement model.

Analysis and findings

In this study, we only considered the level of education of the student at the tertiary level. Most of the students were undergraduates, females studying at public universities. Among the respondents 154 students were from universities situated in urban, 103 from semi-urban, and 81 from rural areas but, most of the students reside in urban areas which were 201. Approximately 62% of the respondents use broadband service and the rest of the 38% students use 3G and 4G services from the telecommunication companies operating in Bangladesh. The source fund of the 40% students are family and self, whereas 4% of the students rely on scholarship only to meet their educational expense. 134 out of 338 respondents are studying business. On the other hand, 87 respondents were from arts, 71 respondents were from applied science, and 46 respondents were from engineering.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics

	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Level of education	Graduate	134	40%
	Undergraduate	204	60%
Gender	Male	158	47%
	Female	180	53%
Type of University	Public	285	84%
	Private	53	16%

Characteristics		Frequency	Percentage
Location of the Student's Residence	Urban	201	59%
	Semi-urban	90	27%
	Rural	47	14%
Location of the University	Urban	154	46%
	Semi-urban	103	30%
	Rural	81	24%
Type of ISP	Telecom Companies	127	38%
	Broadband	211	62%
Source of Fund	Self	27	8%
	Family	52	15%
	Family and Self	136	40%
	Scholarship	14	4%
	Scholarship and Self	31	9%
	Scholarship, Family, and Self	78	23%
Discipline	Applied Science	71	21%
	Engineering	46	14%
	Business	134	40%
	Arts	87	26%
Total Respondents		338	

Measurement model

The first step in the study is to ensure that the measurement models can be used in the case of graduate, undergraduate, and combined settings (Hair et al. 2014). Analyzing the measurement model requires determining whether or not the model's latent variables (LVs) are valid and reliable. Convergent and discriminant validity are two subcategories of validity. It is necessary to look at the relationships between the LVs and their related items in order to determine whether the model is reliable and valid, and this is done using two important coefficients: Extraction of composite reliability and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) (Chin, 2010; Hair et al., 2011, Tirno et al., 2020). When evaluating the reliability of a model, it is necessary to calculate the loading of each indication on its related LV and compare it to a predetermined threshold. In general, for indication reliability to be deemed adequate, the loading should be greater than 0.7. (Hair et al. 2011). In general, if an item's loading is less than 0.4, it should be considered for removal; however, objects with loadings between 0.4–0.7 should be considered for removal if their CR and AVE climb above the threshold (Chin 2010; Hair et al. 2011).

It was discovered through analysis of the study that all of the indicator loadings on their respective values of LVs were greater than 0.700 for the respondents from both groups as well as the complete dataset. Both groups and the complete dataset had CR values more than or equal to 0.700 for all of the LVs included in the measurement model. As a result of these findings, it may be concluded that the measurement model has adequate reliability. It is also necessary to analyze the convergent validity of the measurement model for both groups, and the AVE of the LVs must be greater than 0.500 to be acceptable (Hair et al., 2018; Happy, 2021; Tirno et al., 2021). Table 3 demonstrates that the AVE of the

constructs was greater than 0.500, indicating that convergent validity was acceptable in this case.

In order to establish discriminant validity, we have conducted Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio which is proven to be an effective measure of discriminant validity than the Fornell-Larcker criterion based on the Monte-Carlo simulation (Hair et al., 2018). If the HTMT is less than 0.800 then, the data set can be declared to have the discriminant validity. Therefore, our analysis of the study supported the threshold (Table 4).

Results of Hypothesis Testing

Both nonparametric approaches, Henseler's MGA (Henseler et al. 2009) and the permutation test (Chin and Dibbern 2010), were used to evaluate the structural model and the MGA (Table 5). Path coefficient differences between two groups can be assessed using the most conventional PLS-SEM approaches. Henseler's MGA compares the group-specific bootstrap estimates from each bootstrap sample directly with one another. When two groups have path coefficients with p values of less than 0.05 or greater than 0.95 (Henseler et al. 2009; Sarstedt et al. 2011), a 5 percent level of significant differences between specific path coefficients has been found. The permutation test produces a p-value, but only if the p-value is less than 0.05 is the difference significant.

Our analysis of the study showed that there weren't any significant differences exist for the relationship of subjective norms with students' intention to use, perceived usefulness (PU), and perceived ease of use (PEOU) to adopt e-learning (H1a, H1a, H1c) in terms graduate and undergraduate students. In contrast, there were significant differences found considering graduate and undergraduate students for the relationship between computer self-efficacy (CSE) with students' intention to adopt e-learning (H2a) and CSE with students' perceived ease of use to adopt e-learning (H2b). But there is an insignificant difference found between the relationship with CSE and perceived usefulness (H2c). Whereas, the relationship between PEOU with perceived usefulness (H3a) and PEOU with students' intention to adopt e-learning (H3b) have noteworthy differences considering the level of education of the students. Last but not least, the relationship between perceived usefulness and intention to use e-learning platforms was more or less similar in nature considering the graduate and undergraduate students (H4).

Table 3

Assessment Results of the Measurement Model

Construct and Items	Loading			Composite reliability			Average variance extracted		
	Complete	Graduate	Undergraduate	Complete	Graduate	Undergraduate	Complete	Graduate	Undergraduate
Intention to Use				0.850	0.858	0.848	0.654	0.669	0.650
ITU1	0.816	0.859	0.798						
ITU2	0.828	0.845	0.809						
ITU3	0.781	0.745	0.811						
Perceived Ease of Use				0.872	0.835	0.885	0.629	0.562	0.659
PEOU1	0.812	0.828	0.829						
PEOU2	0.803	0.723	0.820						
PEOU3	0.802	0.636	0.836						
PEOU4	0.756	0.796	0.759						
Perceived Usefulness				0.890	0.905	0.878	0.619	0.657	0.592
PU1	0.849	0.840	0.851						
PU2	0.719	0.835	0.659						
PU3	0.780	0.791	0.761						
PU4	0.826	0.843	0.822						
PU5	0.752	0.740	0.740						
Computer Self-efficacy				0.909	0.882	0.918	0.626	0.554	0.650
CSE1	0.799	0.744	0.819						
CSE2	0.813	0.764	0.833						
CSE3	0.815	0.791	0.819						
CSE4	0.765	0.727	0.782						
CSE5	0.766	0.691	0.789						
CSE6	0.787	0.746	0.795						
Subjective Norm				0.865	0.820	0.882	0.682	0.603	0.714
SN1	0.834	0.713	0.853						
SN2	0.767	0.811	0.784						
SN3	0.872	0.802	0.895						

Table 4
Discriminant Validity (Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio)

	Complete					Graduate					Undergraduate				
	ITU	PEOU	PU	CSE	SN	ITU	PEOU	PU	CSE	SN	ITU	PEOU	PU	CSE	SN
ITU															
PEOU	0.403					0.129					0.606				
PU	0.245	0.449				0.231	0.264				0.27	0.556			
CSE	0.361	0.219	0.076			0.508	0.214	0.128			0.296	0.343	0.083		
SN	0.22	0.15	0.053	0.265		0.302	0.175	0.101	0.32		0.191	0.227	0.076	0.256	

Table 5
Results of Hypothesis Testing

Path	Path Coefficient		Confidence Interval (95%)		Path Coefficient Difference	P-value Difference (One-tailed)	
	Graduate	Undergraduate	Graduate	Undergraduate		Henseler's MGA	Permutation test
H1a SN -> ITU	-0.127*	-0.058 ^{NS}	[-0.258, -0.019]	[-0.182, 0.081]	-0.069	0.729	0.271
H1b SN -> PEOU	0.068 ^{NS}	-0.143*	[-0.267, 0.259]	[-0.254, -0.022]	0.211	0.134	0.134
H1c SN -> PU	-0.015 ^{NS}	0.026 ^{NS}	[-0.165, 0.188]	[-0.085, 0.142]	-0.041	0.637	0.363
H2a CSE -> ITU	0.391***	0.098 ^{NS}	[0.216, 0.527]	[-0.034, 0.232]	0.293	0.011	0.011
H2b CSE -> PEOU	-0.142 ^{NS}	0.268***	[-0.321, 0.142]	[0.130, 0.381]	-0.410	0.992	0.008
H2c CSE -> PU	0.025 ^{NS}	-0.169**	[-0.219, 0.211]	[-0.281, -0.061]	0.195	0.093	0.093
H3a PEOU -> ITU	0.045 ^{NS}	0.436***	[-0.116, 0.233]	[0.284, 0.568]	-0.392	0.997	0.003
H3b PEOU -> PU	0.235*	0.526***	[-0.136, -0.355]	[0.413, 0.619]	-0.291	0.995	0.005
H4 PU -> ITU	0.183*	0.003 ^{NS}	[-0.032, -0.320]	[-0.121, 0.139]	0.180	0.086	0.086

Note1: NS $p > 0.05$, * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, *** $p \leq 0.001$

Note2: In Henseler's MGA method, the p-value lower than 0.05 or higher than 0.95 indicates at the 5% level significant differences between specific path coefficients across two groups (Henseler, 2012)

Discussions

At the beginning of our study, we had hypothesized nine hypotheses under four basic relationships among the variables. Though several studies showed supported the hypotheses in a combine manner but there wasn't any evidence found that explains the effect of the exogenous variables on the endogenous variable students' intention to use the e-learning platforms. So, there is question still remains unaddressed whether any difference in results transpire considering the level of education: graduate students and undergraduate students. Primarily we had hypothesized that there is a significant difference exist in the

relationship between the exogenous and the endogenous variables considering the level of education of the students in tertiary level. We had also arranged a post focus group discussion to intervene the anomalies in the results.

Our analysis of the study exhibited mixed state on the hypotheses. Among the nine sub-hypotheses under four basic hypotheses, it was found that four sub-hypotheses were found to be true based on our sample data. We did not find any difference on the graduate students' perspective with undergraduate students' perspective on the relationship between subjective norms with students' intention to use, perceived usefulness, and perceived ease of use of the e-learning platforms. When we conducted a focus group discussion, most of the participants said that people who has influence on them are mostly not focused on their academic performance or family members who are technologically handicap. Therefore, they do not seem to have any influence on the perceived usefulness, ease of use or intention to adapt e-learning. In case of both graduate and undergraduate students, most of the family members believed that e-learning is not efficient enough like physical and practical classes in a school setting. Same results comply with the impact of computer self-efficacy on perceived usefulness as well as impact of perceived usefulness on students' intention to adapt e-learning whether s/he is a graduate or undergraduate student. Based on the perspective of the members of our focus group, both graduate and undergraduate students did not have any intention to go for e-learning rather they were interested for physical classes on graduate schools. Therefore, they were pushed for e-learning in the perspective of Bangladeshi students whether they feel its effective or not to them.

Our study showed, students' computer self-efficacy made a vital difference between the two experimental groups. In the perspective of Bangladesh, under-graduate students are using new technology products from an early stage of life. The introduction of ICT course from secondary and higher secondary level also boosted their technopathy. Surprisingly it was found through our focus group discussion and the SEM analysis that, though user friendly interface of the e-learning platforms facilitates the intention to adapt e-learning for both graduate and undergraduate students but survey data indicates otherwise. Our survey data showed undergraduate students' perception of the impact of user friendliness of a e-learning system has more positive significant effect on intention to adapt it or perceived usefulness than the graduate students. The most possible explanation might be that, fresh undergraduate students tend to have more technopathy than the graduate students in an overall sense. Therefore, they have a proclivity to explore new technologies which in turn lead to a positive perceived ease of use and their perceived usefulness along with intention to adapt the technology.

Limitations

Small sample size and non-random selection were acknowledged as the limitations of this research study. The study only included the students' perceptions, not the teachers. The effective implementation of online learning highly depends on both the acceptance level of teachers and students. As a result, the inclusion of students' perspectives might not illustrate the big picture. The selection of only higher education might be considered as another important limitation. A study on private universities might produce more critical results. Another limitation is the study used a conceptual framework which is adapted from

Yuen and Ma, 2008, there can be used other exogenous variables such as technology access, online learning skills, experience, computer anxiety, or other individual factors for the link of perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and behavioural intention. Moreover, this research only focuses on the direct effect rather mediating effect can also be considered to get more comprehensive results.

Conclusion and Future Direction

E-learning measure is considered one of the most momentous recent advancements in the information system industry (Wang, 2003). Adopting online learning is the most suitable option for sustainable educational activities to compensate for the big pause in traditional learning approaches due to the COVID-19 crisis. The study investigates the acceptance of e-learning between graduate and undergraduate students using the TAM model who resided in urban, semi-urban, and rural areas. In general, the results indicated partial support for the TAM model.

Several implications can be drawn from the study: the most important contribution is the use of an illustrious intention-based model in higher education which is a top concern during COVID-19. The present situation demands the use of technology more than before because of distance learning or online learning students are bound to adapt despite their willingness or availability. Another side is to explore the comparison of the perception between graduate and undergraduate students. The results illustrate the significance of graduate students having higher computer self-efficacy on intention to use than undergraduate though the number of undergraduate students is higher than graduates. Therefore, various training programs or workshops can be conducted to improve the self-efficacy of undergraduate-level students.

The authors recommended that The application of this model can be drawn in a different context such as differences in perception of gender, differences in perception of the first year and final year students, differences in perception of public and private university students, and so on. As this research focuses only on the direct effect and only on the comparison between undergraduate and graduate students in higher education, future research can explore the mediating effect as well as the comparison between public and private higher education or between different developing countries. Moreover, the longitudinal technique can be adopted in order to observe the differences in pandemic and regular situations. Davis (1993) also recommends the use of additional factors to be included in the original TAM model. Consequently, future studies can be included the role of additional factors.

Declaration of Conflicting Interests

The authors professed no potential conflicts of interest regarding the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

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